

Synthesis of New 5,12-Dihydroxy-6,11-dioxo-2-azanaphthacenes from 5,8-Dimethoxy-2-tosyl-1,2-dihydroisoquinolines

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Manuscript received 15 May 1992, revised 14 September 1992, accepted 21 September 1992

The ellipticine, 8-methoxyellipticine, 9-hydroxy-2-methylellipticinium acetate, olivacine and related 6*H*-pyrido[4,8-*b*]carbazoles are used in the treatment of various malignant diseases^{1,2}. These compounds are planar and they intercalate between the base pairs of DNA. The intercalation and their further reactions with DNA are responsible for their biological activities³. The synthesis of 2-azanaphthacene and their derivatives have been undertaken with the premise that the combination of the chromophore of antitumor anthracycline⁴ and ellipticine might increase the biological activity of the newer 2-azanaphthacyclines.

Recently we have reported the synthesis of 5,12-dihydroxy-6,11-dioxo-1-azanaphthacenes and related azanaphthacenes by cyclocondensation reaction of phthalic anhydride with 5,8-dimethoxyquinolines^{5,6}, 5,8-dimethoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinolines and 5,8-dimethoxyquinoxaline⁸. Now we report the cyclocondensation reaction of phthalic anhydride with 5,8-dimethoxy-2-tosyl-1,2-dihydroisoquinolines under sodium aluminium chloride melt conditions.

The required 5,8-dimethoxy-2-tosyl-1,2-dihydroisoquinoline (2) was synthesised by Jackson's modification in Pomeranz-Fritch isoquinoline synthesis^{9,10}. Similarly, 5,8-dimethoxy-2-tosyl-1-methyl-1,2-dihydroisoquinoline (5) was synthesised by following the same method. The cyclocondensation of 5,8-dimethoxy-2-tosyl-1,2-dihydroisoquinoline (2) with phthalic anhydride gave 5,12-dihydroxy-6,11-dioxo-2-azanaphthacene (3) and 5,12-dihydroxy-6,11-dioxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-2-azanaphthacene (4) (Scheme 1). The acid-catalysed detosylation of 2 may lead to the corresponding 5,8-dimethoxyisoquinoline⁹ which may also be formed by the acid-catalysed disproportionation of 2 along with the corresponding 5,8-dimethoxy-2-tosyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline¹¹. The cyclocondensation of phthalic anhydride with the above aromatic and tetrahydroisoquinoline leads to the formation of 3 and 4.

The cyclocondensation of phthalic anhydride (1) with 5,8-dimethoxy-1-methyl-2-tosyl-1,2-dihydroisoquinoline (5) gave only 5,12-dihydroxy-6,11-dioxo-1-methyl-2-azanaphthacene (6).

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on a Thomas-Hoover-Unimelt capillary melting point apparatus. Ir spectra

were recorded on a Shimadzu IR 435 or a Perkin-Elmer FT-1710 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Shimadzu 260 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrometer or a Jeol FX-100 (100 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal reference and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS D 300 spectrometer using EI method (70 eV).

5,8-Dimethoxy-2-tosyl-1,2-dihydroisoquinoline (2)⁹, 5,8-dimethoxy-1-methyl-2-tosyl-1,2-dihydroisoquinoline (5)¹⁰ and 5,8-dimethoxyisoquinoline⁹ were prepared by modification of the reported procedures.

Reaction of phthalic anhydride (1) with 5,8-dimethoxy-2-tosyl-1,2-dihydroisoquinoline (2): A mixture of 5,8-dimethoxy-2-tosyl-1,2-dihydroisoquinoline (2; 0.68 g, 0.002 mol) and phthalic anhydride (1; 0.674 g, 0.0045 mol) was added to aluminium chloride (6.7 g, 0.05 mol) and sodium chloride (1.34 g, 0.023 mol) melt kept at 185–90° under nitrogen atmosphere and maintained at that temperature for 5 min. The resultant mass was cooled to 0° and treated with a saturated aqueous solution of oxalic acid (75 ml) with stirring and the stirring was continued for 4 h to give an orange coloured solution, which was extracted with dichloromethane (3 × 100 ml), dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent evaporated. The resulting residue was chromatographed on a silica gel column with benzene as the eluent to give 5,12-dihydroxy-6,11-dioxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-2-tosyl-2-azanaphthacene (4; 6%, 0.057 g), m.p. 234–35°; λ_{max} (ε): 233.4 (53.0), 251.8 (58.3), 257.6 (55.8), 282.8 (16.0) and 482.0 nm (11.7); ν_{max} (nujol) 1 620, 1 480, 1 150, 990 and 730 cm⁻¹; δ(CDCl₃) 2.44 (3H s, 4-CH₃), 3.00 (2H, m, H-4), 3.36 (2H, m, H-3), 4.30 (2H, s, H-1), 7.38 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, H-3' and H-5'), 7.80 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz, H-2' and H-6'), 7.82 (2H, m, H-8 and H-9), 8.36 (2H, m, H-7 and H-10) and 13.80 (2H, s, 2 × OH); *m/z* (rel. int.) 449 (20.0), 294 (100.0), 293 (63.0), 267 (23.0) and 266 (42.0).

Further elution of the column with chloroform gave 5,12-dihydroxy-6,11-dioxo-2-azanaphthacene (3; 56%, 0.22 g) m.p. >300° (lit.¹² >300°); λ_{max} (ε) (CH₂Cl₂) 261.2 (16.4), 482.4 (4.1), 512.6 (4.3) and 552 nm (2.7); ν_{max} (nujol) 1 620, 1 575, 1 300, 1 260, 1 210, 1 020, 820 and 720 cm⁻¹; *m/z* (rel. int.) 291 (100.0), 263.0 (3.0), 235 (1.0), 234 (4.0), 207 (1.0), 206 (1.0), 177 (3.5) and 178 (3.0).

NOTES

Scheme 1

The structure of 3 was confirmed by comparing the different spectral data with that of the authentic samples of 5,12-dihydroxy-6,11-dioxo-2-azanaphthacene^{1a} prepared by the condensation of phthalic anhydride with 5,8-dimethoxyisoquinoline in sodium aluminium chloride melt in 42% yield.

Reaction of phthalic anhydride (1) with 5,8-dimethoxy-1-methyl-2-tosyl-1,2-dihydroisoquinoline (5): A mixture of 5 and phthalic anhydride (1) was cyclocondensed as in the case of 2. The dichloromethane extract was dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporation of the solvent gave a residue which was chromatographed on a silica gel column using benzene as eluent to give 5,12-dihydroxy-6,11-dioxo-1-methyl-2-azanaphthacene (6; 80%), m.p. 265–66°; λ_{max} (ϵ) (CH_2Cl_2) 234.4 (75.4), 263.8 (70.5), 493.2 (20.0) and 526.8 nm (15.1); ν_{max} (nujol) 1 620, 1 600, 1 300, 1 250 and 710 cm^{-1} ;

δ (CDCl_3) 3.23 (3H, s, CH_3), 7.86 (2H, m, H-8 and H-9), 8.14 (1H, d, J 6 Hz, H-3), 8.48 (2H, m, H-7 and H-10) and 8.82 (1H, d, J 6 Hz, H-3); m/z (rel. int.) 305.0 (100) and 277.0 (12.0).

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance by the C.S.I.R., New Delhi is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. L. M. WERBEL, M. ANGELO, D. W. FRY and D. F. WORTH, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1986, **29**, 1321.
2. P. JURET, J. F. HERON, J. E. COUETTE, T. DELOZIER and J. Y. LE TALAER, *Cancer Treat. Rep.*, 1982, **66**, 1909.
3. M. MATTONCH, R. BESSELIEVRE, B. MONSERRAT, P. LESCA, B. MEUNIER, H. P. HASSON and C. PAOLETTI, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1985, **28**, 708.
4. F. ARCAMONE, "Doxorubicin: Anticancer Antibiotics", Academic, New York, 1981.

5. P. N. H. NIZAR and S. M. S. CHAUHAN, *Org. Pre. Proc. Int.*, 1989, 21, 243.
6. P. N. H. NIZAR and S. M. S. CHAUHAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1990, 29, 984.
7. V. AWASTHI and S. M. S. CHAUHAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1991, 30, 351.
8. M. GUPTA, P. N. H. NIZAR and S. M. S. CHAUHAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, 68, 465.
9. A. J. BIRCH, A. H. JACKSON and P. V. R. SHANNON, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1974, 2185.
10. J. M. BOBBITT and A. J. BOURQUE, *Heterocycles*, 1987, 25, 601.
11. J. KNABEE, *Adv. Heterocycl Chem.*, 1986, 40, 105.
12. L. A. MITSCHER, H. GILL, J. A. FILPPI and R. L. WOLGELMUTH, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1986, 29, 1277.